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MONITORING THE CURRENT STATE AND EFFICIENCY OF THE FUNCTIONING OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES IN UKRAINE DURING THE WAR

Abstract.

The article is devoted to a comprehensive assessment of modern realities and monitoring of the effectiveness of the activities of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine. A retrospective analysis and analytical assessment of the dynamics of organizational and economic indicators of the functioning of agribusiness during the war were carried out. The rates of reduction in the number of business entities in the agricultural sector, in particular operating agricultural enterprises, were established. Negative trends in the reduction of employment, labor productivity and volumes of agricultural production during wartime were identified. It was established that the highest rates of decline in profitability during the war were demonstrated by the average agribusiness - the profit of the average agricultural enterprises decreased by 34.1%, and the loss ratio increased by 2.4 times. The number of agricultural enterprises decreased by almost a quarter - from 47,753 in 2021 to 35,547 in 2024, the total number of people employed in the agricultural sector during the war decreased by 15.6% or by 90 thousand people.

Attention is focused on the fact that in war conditions, domestic agrarians demonstrate high adaptability, self-organization and social stability. The activation of organizational and economic development of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine requires a holistic approach that will combine economic, organizational and social tools.

Keywords: agricultural sector of the economy, agricultural enterprises, employment, labor productivity, efficiency

Introduction

Agricultural enterprises do not simply function under martial law, they adapt to the negative impact of a combination of geopolitical and socio-economic challenges, try to minimize risks and increase the efficiency of economic activity. Despite the large-scale impact of the war, the agricultural sector of the Ukrainian economy has preserved, adapted and optimized the main capacity of the domestic food market and its export component. Thanks to the efforts of the state, business and humanitarian initiatives, it was possible to avoid product shortages and ensure an almost pre-war level of food consumption per capita.

At the same time, the war clearly outlined the vulnerable aspects of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises - excessive risk due to loss or damage to property and products, logistical problems, increased cost of material and technical resources, lack of operating funds, an extremely difficult situation with energy supply, population decline and falling purchasing power.

K. Didur and N. Yatsyna devoted their study to assessing modern trends in the functioning of agricultural enterprises in the face of today's complex geopolitical challenges [1]. The authors carried out a comprehensive assessment of the dynamics of the profitability of agricultural enterprises in modern economic conditions, determined the influence of priority factors on the set of efficiency indicators, outlined a set of existing problem levers that negatively affect the level of profitability of agribusiness entities.

In his study, O. Shevchenko [2] emphasizes the

need for constant monitoring of the state and efficiency of the functioning of agricultural enterprises and the agricultural sector of the economy as a whole. The author notes that objective monitoring and consideration of regional features of the functioning of agricultural enterprises are of great importance for the development of effective strategies for their adaptation to modern challenges.

O. Tomchuk and N. Polishchuk devoted their study to the study of the main problems of the competitiveness of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine during martial law [3]. O. Skydan and V. Kravchenko [4] devoted their study to the comprehensive financial and economic characteristics of the activities of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine in modern economic conditions. The authors identified a set of existing problems, outlined key trends and prospects for gradual development in the conditions of post-war restoration of the agrarian economy.

M. Dyachenko and V. Zhmudenko [5] devoted their study to the assessment of losses and damages suffered by agricultural enterprises as a result of a full-scale war. The authors note that despite the disappointing dynamics of the number of business entities that have suffered significant losses in recent years, the agrarian sector of the Ukrainian economy demonstrates sufficient resilience and adaptability to the challenges of wartime.

In turn, O. Sushchenko and V. Tymkovan [6], I. Lyudvik [7], O. Kovbasa [8] and others devoted their works to comprehensive monitoring of the state and trends of the functioning of the agrarian sector of the

economy in the context of ensuring the country's food security and the development of export activities.

At the same time, comprehensive and objective monitoring of modern trends and the effectiveness of the functioning of agricultural enterprises in the conditions requires further research and systematic assessment.

The purpose of the article is a retrospective assessment of the trends and effectiveness of the functioning of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine during the war.

Results and discussion

A negative trend in the reduction of the total number of business entities in the agricultural sector of the economy during the war has been established. This negative trend is estimated at 7.1% (from 70.8 to 58.7 thousand or by 12,100 units).

It has been established that of the total number of business entities operating in the agricultural sector of the economy of Ukraine, agricultural enterprises account for 60.6%. During 2021-2024, this indicator decreased by almost 7%. Accordingly, the number of agricultural enterprises decreased by almost a quarter - from 47,753 in 2021 to 35,547 in 2024. It should be noted that if in the first year of the war the decrease was 31.2% (14.9 thousand), then in 2023 there was a positive dynamic of the resumption of activity of 25.5% or 8,045 agricultural enterprises. Unfortunately, 2024 added a negative adjustment towards a reduction of 13.1% or 5342 enterprises.

Regarding the assessment of the regional transformation of quantitative indicators of business entities in the agricultural sector of the economy, we note that the disappointing rating of the loss of their production potential is headed by Zaporizhia and Kherson regions. According to the State Statistics Committee, the decrease in the number of agribusiness entities in these regions is 80 and 83.7% (or 3071 and 2777 units).

It should be noted that in percentage terms, the largest reduction in the number of agricultural enterprises was objectively recorded in the Luhansk region - 97% or 1568 units. In the Kharkiv region, the decrease in the

number of business entities was 789 units, every fifth enterprise ceased its economic activity. Odesa and Mykolaiv regions lost 956 and 826 agribusiness entities at the beginning of 2025.

Studies have found that the negative dynamics of the reduction in the number of operating business entities had a corresponding impact on employment indicators, production and sale of agricultural products, and labor productivity. According to the State Statistics Committee, the total number of people employed in the agricultural sector during the war decreased by 15.6% or by 90 thousand people.

Objective realities are the fact of a significant decrease in the profitability of agricultural enterprises and other business entities of the agricultural sector of the economy in the first years of the war. Thus, the total amount of net profit of farmers during 2021-2023 decreased almost 4 times (from 238.6 to 63.5 billion UAH), respectively, the loss increased 4.1 times - to 34.1 billion UAH. The results of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in 2024 relatively corrected this negative trend - net profit, compared to 2023, increased by 2.6 times, to UAH 167.4 billion, which is 30% below the pre-war level. The loss-making rate of enterprises decreased by 25% or UAH 8.5 billion, and the percentage of profitable enterprises was 83.7%, which is only 4.6% below the level of 2021 (Table 1). A similar trend was established for all groups of agricultural enterprises and business entities - catastrophic rates of decline in profitability during 2021-2023 and relatively positive dynamics in 2024.

It was established that the highest rates of decline in profitability in wartime conditions were demonstrated by the average agribusiness - the profit of the average agricultural enterprises decreased by 34.1%, and the loss ratio increased by 2.4 times - from 2.7 to 6.4 billion UAH. It should be noted that this group of agricultural enterprises generates 40.3% of the total net profit of the industry.

Table 1.

Retrospective dynamics of profitability of agricultural enterprises of Ukraine, billion UAH

Indicator	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 to 2021, %
<i>Agricultural sector of the economy as a whole</i>								
Net profit	71.0	93.3	81.6	238.8	86.1	63.5	167.4	70.1
profit	93.9	115.8	108.0	247.1	125.2	97.6	193.0	78.1
loss	22.9	22.5	26.4	8.3	39.1	34.1	25.6	308.4
Percentage of profitable enterprises	86.2	83.0	82.6	88.3	78.4	78.1	83.7	-4.6
<i>Large agricultural enterprises</i>								
Net profit	11.2	5.0	8.7	48.3	18.2	14.8	32.1	66.5
profit	11.2	8.2	12.5	49.2	21.4	19.1	38.1	77.4
loss	-	3.2	3.8	0.9	3.2	4.3	6.0	666.7
Percentage of profitable enterprises	100.0	79.4	75.0	91.8	84.6	79.5	90.4	-1.4
<i>Medium agricultural enterprises</i>								
Net profit	38.5	68.5	40.3	102.4	39.7	23.7	67.5	65.9
profit	45.2	77.9	49.6	105.0	57.1	38.1	73.9	70.4
loss	6.7	9.5	9.3	2.7	17.4	14.4	6.4	237.0
Percentage of profitable enterprises	88.4	81.5	83.9	92.9	80.5	76.6	88.7	-4.2
<i>Small business entities</i>								
Net profit	21.3	19.8	32.6	88.1	28.2	25.0	67.8	77.0
profit	37.5	29.6	45.9	92.9	46.7	40.3	80.9	87.1
loss	16.2	9.9	13.3	4.8	18.5	15.3	13.1	272.9
Percentage of profitable enterprises	86.1	83.1	82.6	88.0	78.3	78.2	83.5	-4.5
<i>of which micro-entities</i>								
Net profit	4.9	5.8	10.7	25.1	6.5	7.9	24.2	96.4
profit	12.5	11.2	16.6	28.0	14.6	14.4	29.1	103.9
loss	7.6	5.4	5.8	2.9	8.2	6.5	4.9	169.0
Percentage of profitable enterprises	86.0	83.4	82.3	87.1	77.7	78.0	82.7	-4.4

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [9]

Large agricultural enterprises currently generate 19.3% of the total net profit. During 2021-2024, their profitability decreased by 34.5% - from 48.3 to 32.1 billion UAH., while the percentage of profitable enterprises almost corresponds to the pre-war level - 90.4%.

The lowest rate of profit decline was established for the group of micro-entities of economic activity - only 3.6% or 0.9 billion UAH, but the loss-making of micro-enterprises increased by 1.7 times, which is 2 billion UAH. The percentage of profitable enterprises decreased from 87.1 to 82.7%.

The net profit of small enterprises decreased by 23% during the war, with a corresponding increase in losses by 2.7 times or by 8.3 billion UAH. 83.5% of enterprises completed the 2024 economic year with a profit, which is 4.5 points less than the pre-war period.

The sphere of small and micro entrepreneurship of the agricultural sector of the economy forms the largest share of the total net profit - 40.5%. Despite significant inflation rates and devaluation of the national currency, the volume of manufactured goods in monetary terms decreased by almost 16% - from 1030.3 to 868.7 billion UAH. It was found that production per 1 employed person remained practically at the level of 2021, and the corresponding indicator for sold products increased by 11.5% - from 1637.7 to 1825.6 thousand UAH per 1 employed person

A retrospective analysis of the transformational changes that occurred in the production of agricultural products during the war by regional structure revealed positive dynamics in the western regions of Ukraine (Table 2).

Table 2.

**Dynamics of agricultural production in Ukraine by regional aspect,
billion UAH (in constant 2021 prices), 2018 - 2024.**

Regions	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 to 2021.%
Ukraine	1266.5	1284.3	1154.5	1344.3	1004.2	1115.5	1077.9	80.2
Vinnitsia	104.7	105.7	90.2	110.0	88.5	105.1	97.9	89.0
Volynskaya	29.6	29.9	30.1	30.9	29.9	29.9	30.9	100.0
Dnipropetrovsk	74.3	81.6	70.0	85.4	70.1	80.9	69.8	81.7
Donetsk	31.6	38.4	36.8	39.8	11.1	11.4	8.1	20.4
Zhytomyr	49.9	50.2	48.0	53.8	44.7	47.7	50.4	93.7
Zakarpattia	15.8	15.9	15.4	14.2	14.2	14.7	14.4	101.4
Zaporizhzhia	41.1	53.2	47.1	55.2	13.8	8.7	7.5	13.6
Ivano-Frankivsk	24.5	23.8	24.7	26.0	25.5	26.2	26.8	103.1
Kyiv	81.7	74.8	62.9	74.8	59.2	72.3	70.0	93.6
Kirovohrad	64.8	69.6	49.2	71.9	61.9	68.2	58.9	81.9
Luhansk	25.0	28.5	25.3	27.2	7.7	6.3	6.0	22.1
Lviv	40.9	41.1	43.0	46.2	47.7	48.1	51.8	112.1
Mykolaiv	47.9	51.2	39.1	57.3	32.6	42.7	39.6	69.1
Odessa	62.3	55.0	33.6	64.4	44.2	54.2	57.8	89.8
Poltava	86.0	82.2	73.1	80.0	81.4	84.1	72.9	91.1
Rivne	30.3	30.1	31.1	31.6	30.2	31.8	33.5	106.0
Sumy	57.7	57.6	59.9	53.9	51.0	50.5	46.6	86.5
Ternopil	45.6	44.5	44.6	50.5	48.4	52.6	54.1	107.1
Kharkiv	73.5	75.3	73.9	72.5	33.6	46.9	47.5	65.5
Kherson	54.0	56.4	53.5	60.8	3.0	2.7	5.0	8.2
Khmelnyskyi	68.1	66.0	64.4	73.1	65.9	72.0	74.8	102.3
Cherkasy	77.5	75.6	59.6	80.3	69.6	79.2	72.4	90.2
Chernivtsi	19.0	18.2	18.2	19.8	18.1	19.7	19.4	98.0
Chernihiv	60.7	59.3	61.1	64.5	51.7	59.6	61.6	95.5

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [9]

During 2022-2024, farmers in Lviv region increased the volume of agricultural production by 12.1% (from 46.2 to 51.8 billion UAH). Similar indicators based on the results of the activities of business entities in Ternopil, Rivne and Ivano-Frankivsk regions were 7.1, 6.0 and 3.1%, respectively. Agricultural production by farmers in Rivne region increased by 1.4%, and in Volyn region - remained at the pre-war level in 2021. The largest reduction in agricultural production occurred in the agricultural sector of Kherson region - by 91.8% or by 55.8 billion UAH. The corresponding indicators of the decrease in the production potential of farmers in Zaporizhzhia, Donetsk and Luhansk regions were 86.4, 79.6 and 77.8%, respectively.

Production volumes in regions close to the front have also decreased significantly. Thus, compared to the pre-war period, farmers in Kharkiv region will receive 34.5% less agricultural output (or UAH 25 billion), in Mykolaiv region – 30.9% (or UAH 17.7 billion), in Dnipropetrovsk region – almost 20% (or UAH 15.6 billion), in Sumy region – 13.5% (or UAH 7.3 billion).

Conclusions. It was established that in wartime conditions, the agricultural sector of the Ukrainian economy forms almost 60% of the total structure of Ukrainian exports and 7.1% of the country's GDP. A negative trend in the reduction of the total number of business entities in the agricultural sector of the economy during the war was identified. The rate of decrease is 17.1% (from 70.8 thousand in 2021 to 58.7 thousand

in 2024). In turn, the decrease in the number of agricultural enterprises during the war was almost 25% or 12.2 thousand units.

The rate of reduction in the profitability of agricultural enterprises during 2021-2023 was determined - almost 4 times (from 238.6 to 63.5 billion UAH), respectively, the loss increased 4.1 times - to 34.1 billion UAH. The results of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in 2024 relatively corrected this negative trend - net profit, compared to 2023, increased by 2.6 times, to UAH 167.4 billion, which is 30% lower than the pre-war level.

The extremely difficult economic situation in Ukraine and its agricultural sector requires the intensification and improvement of practical mechanisms for state support for agricultural enterprises and other economic entities, because ensuring food security and replenishing the revenue part of the country's budget with export revenues remains a priority task. Even in wartime conditions, the government introduced a number of instruments to support agricultural enterprises, in particular, preferential lending, granting grants for the restoration of production, simplification of tax rules, various subsidy programs.

From the point of view of regulatory policy, an important direction is the creation of a stable and predictable environment for the organizational and economic development of domestic agribusiness.

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